

Contemporary Issues in Psychological Sciences

Review Article

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Psychology is the science of behavior and mind. Psychology includes the study of conscious and unconscious phenomena, as well as feeling and thought. It is an academic discipline of immense scope. Psychologists seek an understanding of the emergent properties of brains, and all the variety of phenomena linked to those emergent properties, joining this way the broader neuroscientific group of researchers. As a social science it aims to understand individuals and groups by establishing general principles [4, 5].

Major schools of psychology are the Biological, Cognitive, behavioral, social, psychoanalysis, and existential-humanistic theories/approaches. The most important themes include: motivation, emotions, cognition, personality, unconscious processes development and genes and environment. On the other hand, there are many research methodologies for investigating these themes, such as: experimental and statistical method, technological, computer methods, animal studies, qualitative and descriptive researches,

clinical methods, longitudinal-developmental researches, comparative methods [1].

Recently, the most significant and critical issues in researching and investigating the behavior relating to the methodology and the type of studies that have been used.

I can summarize the critical issue by devising the strategies and then methodology into two trends: Naturalistic-empirical and humanistic-clinical approaches.

The efforts of psychologists and clinicians can be related relatively, to one of these strategies regarding the subjects/themes on one hand, and the methodology on the other hand.

I can distinguish between the variables of these trends and strategies as the following:

Variable	Naturalistic-experimental trend	Humanistic-clinical trend
Main field	Experimental psychology (General psychology and normal personality)	Clinical psychology (Abnormal psychology & personality)
Subjects/themes	General - mental processes	Behavioral problems
Awareness	Consciousness	Unconsciousness
Experience	Observing the external behavior	Alive - experiences
Parts/whole	Parts before whole	Whole before parts
Correlations	Quantitative correlations	Qualitative correlations
Facts	Physical facts	Human/spiritual facts
The purpose and the values	Reject the subjective	Accept the subjective
Comparative	Comparative with animals	Comparative inter-and intra- individuals
Controlling variables	High	Low
Difficulties	More Limitations and difficulties of manipulating the subjects of behavior	Low limitations and difficulties of manipulating the behavior
Accuracy	Scientific accuracy	Lack of scientific accuracy
Stubbornness	High Rigidity & stubbornness	Low rigidity
Tests and measurement	Whole indications	Partial indications among Whole personality

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In sum, Ethical standards in the discipline have changed over time [3]. Current ethical guidelines state that using non-human animals for scientific purposes is only acceptable when the harm (physical or psychological) done to animals is outweighed by the benefits of the research. Keeping this in mind, psychologists can use certain research techniques on animals that could not be used on humans.

The theme/subjects of psychology is behavior, but the human behavior is more complex for investigating, and the multi-methodologies are very significant for good understanding, controlling and predicting behavior [2].

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